

75kW Medium Frequency Transformer design based in IPT for Medium Voltage Solid State Transformer applications

Juan Blanco Ortiz ^{1,†,*} , Ignacio González Prieto ² and Mario J. Durán ²

¹ Fundación CIRCE; circe@fcirce.es

² Universidad de Málaga; uma@uma.es

* Correspondence: jblanco@fcirce.es; Tel.: +34 692635719 (J.B.O.)

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract: The evolution of the power grid is increasingly demanding enhanced controllability, driven by the high penetration of renewable energy sources, which introduce variability and decentralization. Furthermore, the rise in DC generation and consumption has led to a growing prevalence of hybrid AC/DC networks, requiring new strategies for efficient power conversion and management. To address these challenges in MV and HV electric grids, the Solid-State Transformer (SST) emerges as a promising solution. However, one of the key challenges in SST design lies in achieving reliable insulation between the high-voltage and low-voltage sections. This paper presents the design and optimization of a high-insulation medium frequency transformer (MFT) for high voltage grids (66 kV) operating at 50 kHz with maximum power of 75 kW for SST using Inductive Power Transfer (IPT) technology. A fixed distance of 50 mm is used between the primary and secondary windings which is filled with dielectric oil. The proposed inductive power transfer (IPT) system employs a double-D coil design, developed by extending the design methodology of a rectangular coil configuration. Initial inductance values required for the SST were determined using the rectangular coil geometry. Subsequently, the double-D coil was implemented within the same spatial constraints as the original rectangular design, enabling a direct comparison of performance and scalability. The rectangular coil design produces significant stray magnetic fields which cause excessive heating in the enclosure, quantified at approximately 269.6 W based on FEM simulations. The double-D coil configuration solves this problem by channelling the magnetic flux along a more controlled path, thereby reducing enclosure losses to only 4.38 W. This optimization results in a 42.4% reduction in overall system losses while maintaining the main electrical parameters.

Keywords: IPT; SST; MFT; High insulation; High Voltage; Magnetics Design; double-D

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1. Introduction

The decarbonization of energy systems is driving significant transformations in the structure and operation of modern power grids. These changes require more interconnected and flexible grid infrastructures capable of handling bi-directional power flows, both AC and DC, and adapting to the evolving needs of electricity transmission and distribution [1]. Conventional high-power transformers face limitations in meeting the requirements of these advanced grid systems, since they are passive components that cannot control the power direction. As a result, Solid-State Transformers (SSTs) are emerging as an innovative solution, offering enhanced control, flexibility, and adaptability to support the dynamic demands of modern power grids and the integration of AC and DC loads and generation [2–5].

The Medium Frequency Transformer (MFT) is the core component of the SSTs, providing key functionalities such as galvanic isolation and enhanced modularity [6,7]. The use of MFTs offers several advantages, including reduced size and weight compared to conventional low-frequency transformers, full control of the power flow and flexibility in system design. This flexibility facilitates the implementation of various converter

configurations, including DC/DC, AC/DC, and AC/AC topologies. Such configurations can be realized as monolithic, modular, or semi-modular solutions [8], depending on the specific application requirements. For instance, in applications requiring high voltage or high current levels, modular configurations provide a practical approach by connecting multiple converters in series or in parallel [9–11]. The series connection of the converters combines their output voltages, enabling higher voltage levels. In contrast, when the converters are connected in parallel, their current capacities combine, allowing the system to handle higher current levels. These modular arrangements effectively overcome the constraints imposed by the voltage and current limitations of existing semiconductor technologies [12].

The transformer in this application will be connected to 66 kV grids, requiring rigorous testing to ensure reliability under high-voltage conditions. Among these, the lightning impulse withstand voltage test stands out as one of the most critical assessments due to its high peak voltage requirements. For this scenario, the transformer must withstand 325 kV [13] during a standard 1.2/50 μ s test. This waveform peaks in 1.2 μ s and decays to 50% of the peak voltage within 50 μ s. Additionally, the transformer must endure 140 kV during the applied voltage test. To meet these requirements, the standard specifies a minimum air clearance of 630 mm, which defines the insulation criteria for this transformer.

The core-type transformer and shell-type transformer constructions are the two most common types of MFTs. In the core-type transformer the windings are wound around each leg in a C-shape core. In contrast, shell-type transformers utilise an E-shape core, where both windings are positioned on the center leg. To enhance the insulation voltage capabilities of MFTs, high-voltage (HV) cables (either solid or litz wire) are often employed. These kind of cables are categorized as dry type insulation. The dielectric strength of silicone, PVC, or HDPE used in high voltage cables ranges from 4 kV/mm to 28 kV/mm [14]. However, the significant insulation surrounding each conductor reduces power density and complicates thermal management, as heat dissipation from the wires becomes challenging.

The use of standard cables with potting resins and plates to achieve the required insulation [15] using the core-type construction is another solution that has been explored. Although higher power densities could be achieved, the HV winding surrounded by the resin restricts the power density due to poor winding heat dissipation. In addition, special techniques should be used to ensure that there are no air bubbles in the resin, which lowers the dielectric strength of the insulation system. Instead of potting resin, other authors use the bobbins to achieve the insulation between windings and ground [16]. The bobbin design is complex and also uses air to achieve insulation with the core. The distances should increase to achieve greater insulations and then the stray field and the low power density discard this solution.

Using the shell-type MFT, biodegradable transformer oil and oil impregnated pressboards operating at 5 kHz [17], the insulation achieved was higher than in previous designs. This frequency leads to bigger transformer than the usual MFT with higher operational frequencies. The thermal management of this transformer is better than the previous one as a result of the use of oil and pumps to force the convection. Furthermore, the core does not cover the base or the sides completely, leaving space to allow stray fields. Those stray fields could produce heat over a metallic enclosure due to induction heating, reducing the possible materials for the enclosure to non conductive ones.

Changing the construction topology, other authors presented a split planar configuration [18–20]. This construction is similar to the Induction Power Transfer (IPT) technology in which the primary and secondary are separated in different planes. This type of construction enables the space to introduce insulation between primary and secondary. In this particular case, the use of a dry type insulator makes the heat dissipation of the wires difficult, limiting the power density. Variations on this kind of construction have been made, introducing two coils that superpose in the middle [21]. This construction allows a central part in which the flux magnetic flux is cancelled and cooling plates can be

introduced. This allows for better heating extraction capabilities than the previous designs with a size increase. Other possible connections are proposed, but they have not been studied.

Consequently, in order to fill the gap in achieving high insulation capabilities, effective thermal performance, and low stray fields, the MFT design presented in this paper is based on IPT technology. It utilizes the split planar configuration with dielectric oil, providing sufficient coil spacing to enhance insulation, improve heat dissipation, and minimize stray fields through the double-D coil design, allowing the use of metals for the enclosure. In addition, the design investigates how increasing the space between coils in the same plane increments the coupling coefficient.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a brief discussion of the limitations of the IPT and SST systems. Section 3 introduces a circular coil design, obtaining the inductance values needed to optimize the performance of the complete SST. Section 4 introduces additional steps to obtain a double-D coil configuration. In addition, it is examined the relationship between the diameter of the coil and the distance between the coils in the same plane with different coil sizes and it is evaluated the stray field and the losses in the enclosure. In Section 5, a comparative analysis of the circular coil and the double-D coil is presented. Finally, Section 6 remarks the most significant findings of this study.

2. Induction Power Transfer (IPT) and Solid State Transformers

The design of the MFT for this application is based on IPT technology, which uses magnetic fields to transfer energy between primary and secondary coils without physical contact. Research on IPT technology has been promoted in recent years by the development of Electric Vehicles (EV)[22], allowing a contactless energy transmission between the vehicle and the charger. Unlike traditional wired charging methods, IPT is unaffected by dirt, chemicals, or weather conditions, offering enhanced durability and usability. Recent developments in IPT technology focus on improving efficiency, power delivery while addressing challenges such as misalignment between the charger and vehicle coils and interoperability [23,24]. These advances are crucial because many applications involve mobile coil components. Beyond EVs, IPT technology is also utilized in automated factory logistic vehicles [25], biomedical implants [26,27], harsh environments, underwater power delivery [28], and charging for consumer electronics such as smartphones [29–31], among others.

In MFT design, IPT technology is particularly advantageous for applications that require high-voltage insulation. The gap between the primary and secondary circuits can be filled with dielectric material or fluid, enhancing insulation and enabling operation in medium and high-voltage grids. Unlike EV charging systems, where misalignment is a significant concern, this application benefits from precise manufacturing processes, ensuring minimal misalignment and consistent performance. In addition, this design offers benefits related to heat management and construction precision. The wires are securely fixed within a predefined route, achieving low tolerance and high repeatability in the inductance values. The heat generated by the coils and ferrite is effectively managed as a result of direct contact with dielectric oil or air, which facilitates natural convection. If needed, forced convection can be easily implemented to further enhance heat dissipation.

However, this technology has a drawback because the coupling coefficient plays a crucial role in figuring out the maximum efficiency of the system. Equation 1 [32] establishes the highest efficiency that an IPT system can obtain, and Q and k are the two parameters influencing the efficiency.

$$\eta_{\max} = \frac{k^2 Q_1 Q_2}{\left(1 + \sqrt{1 + k^2 Q_1 Q_2}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

Consequently, the distance needed to ensure the isolation between primary and secondary reduces the efficiency of the overall system, which becomes a critical aspect to consider.

This indicates that not only the coupling coefficient should be taken into account for efficiency but also the coil quality factor Q . The factor Q is defined as equation 2 indicates, having a relation between the coil resistance and impedance. The closer the coil is to the ideal model, the greater is this factor, giving access to higher efficiencies with lower couplings.

$$Q = \frac{\omega L}{R_{ac}} \quad (2)$$

As described in equation 3, the k (magnetic coupling) is related to the magnetising inductance and the inductance of each coil. This is a relationship of how much of the field produced by the primary induced the secondary or vice versa. The greater the magnetising inductance, the greater the coupling coefficient and the efficiency.

$$k = \frac{L_m}{\sqrt{L_1 L_2}} \quad (3)$$

The coupling coefficient (k) and quality factor (Q) are critical parameters for maximising the efficiency of inductive power transfer (IPT) systems. Achieving high efficiency requires careful optimisation of the magnetic design, including the dimensions and configurations of the coils, as well as accounting for environmental factors like the material properties of the surroundings. While these parameters directly influence performance, balancing high efficiency with low losses and robust insulation implies significant challenges, particularly in high-voltage, high-power applications.

However, the inherent challenges of maintaining high efficiency while ensuring adequate insulation and minimizing losses require an iterative design approach. Addressing these challenges is essential for developing an IPT system capable of meeting the demanding requirements of high-voltage, high-power applications. To address these demands, this study adopts a structured iterative design approach, outlined in the following section that integrates the electrical and magnetic behaviour of the transformer.

3. Design Process: Inductance values determination

Magnetic design is typically an iterative process in which various approximations are made until the specified requirements are met. Although reluctance models are often used to estimate the dimensions of the coil and core, their application in IPT systems is challenging due to the large air gap between the primary and secondary coils.

In [33] is developed a reluctance model for IPT systems with primary-to-secondary distances from 100 to 200 mm. However, this approach does not address the challenges introduced by the necessary steel enclosure in the model presented in this work. The enclosure acts as a shield, significantly reducing the magnetic flux returning and, therefore, reducing the inductance obtained in the system. This effect is difficult to model with precision using reluctance methods since the steel has ferromagnetic properties and could change how the magnetic field behaves. To better capture these effects and accurately analyse component losses, 2D FEM simulations are used in this work, providing critical insights into the influence of the steel enclosure, particularly as these losses are vital to the system's thermal management.

The inductance values of the IPT are obtained with a circular coil over a ferrite plane using 2D FEM simulations. This geometry is selected due to its polar symmetry that enables the possibility to use 2D simulations instead of 3D simulations, saving compute time. Furthermore, this geometry provides greater accuracy compared to planar models in 2D, which assume an 'infinite' Z-axis distance or require a depth parameter.

The strategy followed in this paper to obtain the IPT design consists of several simulation steps. The first step involves simple 2D simulations to verify the relationship

between coil diameter and coupling coefficient at a fixed distance of 50 mm. In the second step, a range of diameters is selected to achieve the necessary coupling coefficient, ensuring the desired efficiency based on the maximum efficiency equation. The third step considers the influence of power electronics and analyses various IPT configurations within this diameter range. Finally, the fourth step involves selecting the most suitable option based on the component losses and the voltages achieved.

Initially, a comparison is made between the coil size and the coupling, using a fixed number of four turns per winding. To automate the scaling of both the winding size and the ferrite core in the 2D FEM simulations, a custom script is developed. Additionally, it is easily defined by the outer diameter of the coil and the number of turns. The model prioritizes simplicity. 80 simulations between 150 mm of outer diameter and 1500 mm were performed. The simulation lasts 77 seconds in total, less than one second per case. This study offers preliminary insights that help reduce overall design time by providing optimized starting points for further steps. The FEMM software uses the current and the frequency as excitation of the coils. It only manages one frequency, for this case the resonant frequency of the system.

The results of this preliminary study are shown in Figure 1. The magnetic coupling is strongly dependent on both the distance and the diameter of the coils. As the coil diameter increases, the magnetic coupling and system efficiency also improve.

As in Step 2 of this design process, the diameter range is determined with this result. In this particular system, where high efficiency is required, a coupling coefficient of at least 0.6 is necessary to obtain the efficiency without reaching high Q values. However, this IPT will need low resistance to improve the Q coefficient as much as possible. Consequently, the design exploration begins with an inner coil diameter of 330 mm.

Figure 1. (a) Results of the comparison between the diameter of the coil and the coupling coefficient. (b) Representation of the efficiency equation 1, with different values of Q .

The third step regarding the IPT design configuration is to obtain the inductance values for each IPT and to introduce them into the electrical circuits to verify its behaviour. The schematic of the electric circuit is shown in Figure 2. The resonant tank is in a CLLC configuration, since the IPT does not have great values of magnetising inductance that branch can not be avoided in the calculations and some of the current of the tank is drained from that inductance. The values obtained in the FEMM simulation are translated into a representation of the T model seen from the primary of the transformer. In this particular case, since the turn ratio is 1:1, there are no differences between the inductances from the primary or secondary. The system can be represented with a 2x2 matrix as shown in equation 4. The currents and the power flowing from primary to secondary can be obtained to assess if each IPT is able to transfer the 75 kW, as it can be seen in the equation 5 and equation 6.

Figure 2. Electrical diagram of the resonant tank in a CLLC configuration and the two full bridges with SiC MOSFETs .

$$\begin{bmatrix} j\omega L_1 - j/\omega C_1 & -j\omega M \\ -j\omega M & j\omega L_2 - j/\omega C_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ -V_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{V_1 \cdot Z_M - (Z_1 + Z_M) \cdot V_2}{(Z_M + Z_2)(Z_1 + Z_M) - Z_M^2} \quad (5)$$

$$S_2 = V_2 * I_2^* \quad (6)$$

The script evaluates each possible IPT from 330 to 550 millimetres of ferrite plane, with a minimum of 4 turns up to the maximum number of turns the ferrite plane is able to accommodate. Then each IPT is translated to the T model and introduced in the power electronics model. An evaluation with a range of input and output voltages checks the ZVS operation, measures the phase margin for control purposes, and the total efficiency of the complete system expected, without taking into account the switching losses. The starting point was selected in 330 because the ferrite plates that form the plane are designed to be squares of 55 millimetres. Once the script has evaluate all the IPTs possibilities results are shown in a list with all the geometries that meets the requirements for the power electronics design and control. In order to discriminate between the eleven possibilities, the focus is set in three main aspects, efficiency, size, and the voltage in the capacitors.

First, high efficiency is essential to maintain system competitiveness compared to traditional transformers, as they are highly optimized. Furthermore, higher efficiency impacts the thermal performance of the system. Lower power losses mean less heat generation, which directly influences the cooling requirements, allowing for smaller or no cooling systems, and extending the lifespan of the equipment by avoiding thermal degradation of components.

The size is equally significant because the IPT modules are immersed in dielectric fluid. Reducing the size of each module will decrease the volume of dielectric fluid required, which reduces the material costs and the physical footprint of the system. Beyond this reduction, smaller module dimensions facilitate easier installation and integration into existing grid infrastructure, where space can often be limited. In addition, from a logistical perspective, smaller modules are easier to transport and handle during both the manufacturing and installation phases.

The last criterion for selecting the IPT modules is the voltage across the capacitor. Keeping the voltage as low as possible is critical for several reasons. Firstly, a lower voltage allows for a simpler capacitor configuration, which minimizes the complexity of the design and reduces the risk of imbalance between the capacitors in the tank. The capacitor imbalance can lead to an uneven voltage distribution, which can result in localized overvoltage conditions, premature failure, or reduced system reliability. In addition, a lower voltage reduces the stress on the dielectric materials within the capacitors, extending their operational lifespan and improving overall system durability. Finally, maintaining a lower

voltage simplifies the selection of capacitors and allows for the use of more commercially components, potentially reducing procurement costs and ensuring easier replacement.

The results of the automated study, including power losses, voltage across capacitors and module dimensions, are illustrated in Figure 3. This figure provides a comparison of the various IPT module configurations, 11 possible IPTs met the requirements imposed.

Figure 3. Losses results and maximum voltage over resonant capacitors with the different IPT variations.

The IPT variation number 7 is the selected IPT, which consists of a circular coil with 5 turns, an outer diameter of 540 mm, an inner diameter of 374 mm, and a ferrite plane of 550 mm. The magnetising inductance for this variation is 25 μH . This variation was chosen based on the three main criteria discussed above. It maintains a voltage below 1250 V across the capacitors, and the losses are comparable to other variations when metal case losses are excluded. Variations 7 through 11 all share the same ferrite plane, but as the number of turns increases, core losses decrease while winding losses increase. Since all these variations use the same ferrite plane, variation 7 is preferred due to its lower amount of wire, providing a better balance between core and winding losses. This balance simplifies the thermal management of the system. Additionally, losses in the winding are more difficult to dissipate because the use of tapped litz wire significantly reduces the thermal conductivity.

In this geometry, the magnetic field returns from the ferrite edges, which creates an important amount of stray flux that is encountered by the enclosure if it is positioned too closely. In this design, the distance between the ferrite and the enclosure is 100 mm. However, this distance is insufficient, as the losses in the metal enclosure represent the primary source of energy dissipation. Since this system employs dielectric oil for cooling, minimizing enclosure losses is crucial, especially when natural convection is the primary mechanism for heat transfer. Ideally, the oil should descend along the enclosure walls, cooling as it moves downward, while the oil between the primary and secondary components rises as it heats, facilitating heat extraction from the coils and ferrites. Direct heating of the enclosure could impede the transfer of heat from the coils and cores to the surrounding environment, thereby reducing the system's cooling efficiency and overall performance.

To validate the results regarding the losses in the metal enclosure, which were initially predicted by the 2D simulation, a detailed 3D simulation was conducted using COMSOL Multiphysics. This simulation provided a more comprehensive analysis by modelling

the electromagnetic field interactions and losses within the enclosure. The results of the simulation corroborated the findings of the script, with 269.6 W losses in the metal case. In Figure 4 the distribution of the volumetric electromagnetic losses for the rectangular coil design is shown. This distribution of the losses reveals the path of the returning magnetic field from the primary to the secondary and reveals the hot spots in the enclosure.

Figure 4. Volumetric loss distribution in the IPT enclosure with a rectangular coil design, totalling 269.9 W. The highest losses occur near the edges of the ferrite plane, where an increased stray flux intensifies energy losses in the enclosure.

In order to address this issue with the hot spots in the tank and reduce the losses, different approaches can be taken. The first approach is to increase the distance between the ferrite and the enclosure. However, given that size optimization is a primary design objective, this solution may not be the most feasible.

The second option involves the introduction of magnetic conductor materials, such as ferrite, between the coil and the enclosure to mitigate the magnetic field interaction. Although effective, this solution would result in a more complex mechanical design, potentially increasing the difficulty of prototype fabrication and increasing the total cost, since more ferrite is needed.

Another possibility is to conduct a detailed study of various operational points using 3D Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations to accurately model the loss distribution. Following this, a thermal analysis could be performed using software such as ANSYS Fluent to evaluate the heat dissipation. This method was explored in [34] with promising results for three-phase, three-legged Wye-Wye transformers with only one neutral grounded, although it did not account for zero-sequence stray losses.

In this article, the design process takes two more steps, redefining the geometry of the coil to reduce the stray flux over the enclosure while maintaining the same inductance values to ensure consistent electrical performance, since these values ensure the ZVS operation.

Different coil configurations were studied, such as the D4Q [35], which was not an option due to the increase in copper weight. Also, simple shapes such as hexagonal or circular show the same problem as circular/rectangular [36]. The double-D helps reduce the losses of the aluminium shielding [37] [38], then for this particular case in which the material used in the tank is steel, the reduction of losses should be even greater than the aluminium. This coil configuration aims to prevent the magnetic flux from returning over the edges of the ferrite, thereby reducing enclosure losses and improving overall system efficiency.

4. Design process: double-D coil configuration

The following steps regarding the coil design involve studying the characteristics of the double-D coil. This coil configuration presents several disadvantages when compared to rectangular coils, which need to be considered during the design phase to minimize the total losses and enhance the system's efficiency.

The current of the coils placed in the middle of the ferrite plane have the same direction, this makes an addition of magnetic field in the middle part of the ferrite plane and the amount of ferrite necessary to maintain the magnetic flux density should be doubled. For this design, the maximum desired magnetic flux density is 0.15 T or below. The ferrite plane from the previous steps is maintained, hence the magnetic flux in that part is expected to increase and consequently increase the core losses.

Copper losses increase as a result of the larger volume of material required. The higher amount of copper exposed to magnetic fields also results in slightly more AC resistance effects. Given the operating frequency of 47 kHz for this type of transformer, litz wire is a suitable solution, as it reduces AC losses compared to solid wire, and the ratio between DC and AC losses should be less than 1.5 the DC resistance as studied in [39].

The next step involves a preliminary study of the expected magnetic field behaviour with this geometry. A 2D FEM simulation was performed to obtain the Figure 5 which shows the flux distribution of the double-D configuration. Furthermore, a qualitative reluctance model shown in Figure 6 was made to model the flux observed in the simulation.

Figure 5. Flux distribution in the double-D arrangement. The purple areas denote the concatenated flux linking the primary and secondary coils, labelled as ϕ_{m1} and ϕ_{m2} . The green areas correspond to the leakage flux confined within the generating coil, identified as ϕ_{l1} , ϕ_{l2} , and ϕ_{l3} .

Figure 6. Qualitative reluctance model. The reluctances model represents the different magnetic flux paths shown in Figure 5. The colours of the reluctances corresponds to the respective magnetic flux region, facilitating a clear correlation between flux distribution and its associated reluctances.

In Figure 5, there are two zones of flux that concatenate the primary and the secondary, ϕ_{m1} and ϕ_{m2} . The leakage flux is named as ϕ_{l1} , ϕ_{l2} , and ϕ_{l3} . Performing a comparison with the rectangular coil configuration, one of these two magnetic fluxes (ϕ_{m1} or ϕ_{m2}) returned over the edges of the geometry, causing the problem of inducing the enclosure of the system.

The leakage flux in the rectangular coil is inside the coils and is only dependent on the distance between primary and secondary, and the diameter of the coil, which is the flux that is not linked with the secondary. In contrast, in this double-D configuration, the flux ϕ_{m2} is inside the ferrite plane. Moreover, the main leakage flux occurs in the ϕ_{l2} zone, where the flux flows from one coil to the other coil in the same plane.

Therefore, with the double-D configuration there is a better controllability of the flux path for the magnetising and leakage flux. Some part of the leakage flux is outside the ferrite plane as the ϕ_{l1} and ϕ_{l3} zones show but is not the major part. Then, is expected to have less flux inducing the enclosure to reduce the losses from the 300 W initially obtained with the rectangular coil.

In Figure 6, the model reflects the different fluxes in reluctances. Reluctances R_{l11} , R_{l12} , and R_{l13} refer to the flux path ϕ_{l1} , ϕ_{l2} and ϕ_{l3} , and reluctances R_{gap} reflect the path for ϕ_{m1} and ϕ_{m2} . The colour of the reluctances matches the colours of the flux of the image 5, having the purple for the linked flux between primary and secondary and the green for the leakage flux.

This representation reveals the better controllability of the leakage flux in the double-D coil configuration. The main source of leakage inductance is the zone of ϕ_{l2} and R_{l12} , then increasing the distance between the coils should decrease the amount of flux linking both coils on the primary side, increasing the reluctance R_{l12} , reducing the value of the leakage inductance of the system. Increasing the reluctance R_{l12} while maintaining the other reluctances at the same value should increase the magnetising inductance since more flux will be able to pass through the R_{gap} reluctance. A series of 2D simulations was conducted to examine the relationships among coil diameter, the distance between coils on the same plane (D-D distance), the coupling coefficient and the magnetising inductance.

Figure 7. Coupling and magnetising inductance for several coil diameters.

Similarly to the analysis performed for the rectangular coil, this set of simulations aimed to establish a range of parameters for the final solution using this new geometry. Furthermore, these calculations were intended to corroborate the relationship between coupling and the inductances explained in Figure 5. The simulations were carried out in FEMM using the planar solver, as the double-D geometry lacks polar symmetry, with a simulation depth of 550 mm. Each coil consisted of four turns, matching the configuration of the rectangular coil used in preliminary tests. To verify the results of the simulation set, the outer diameter of the coil is designated as D , and the center-to-center distance between the coils is denoted as d . The graph represents the ratio D/d , where $d/D = 1$ indicates that there is no separation between the coils. Various values of D are represented to explore how variations in this parameter affect the results.

The resulting graph from the 2D simulations is shown in Figure 7. These results align with the conclusions drawn from Figure 5. It can be observed that the size of the coil is the dominant factor influencing the magnetising inductance and coupling. Furthermore, increasing the distance between the coils enhances the magnetising inductance but does not have a substantial impact on the coil size (represented by D). The coupling coefficient also correlates with coil diameter; as diameter increases, so does the coupling, similar to the behaviour observed in the rectangular coil design.

However, the distance d becomes more critical when D is smaller. Increasing d can enhance the coupling coefficient up to 0.05, thus improving the efficiency of the system. This increase in the coupling effect is due to two effects: a slight increase in the magnetising inductance and a decrease in the leakage inductance. Therefore, the maximum leakage inductance is obtained when $d/D = 1$, as explained in Figure 5.

To determine the approximate size of the double-D coils, since the value of the magnetising inductance is defined in the previous steps, and this value of inductance defines the electrical behaviour of the complete system, the coil diameter should be approximately 220-230 mm according to the results obtained.

A new set of 3D simulations were performed in order to obtain a better model with higher accuracy with the losses and the inductance calculated. These simulations are not performed with scripts and are not automated. The geometry is designed with parameters that can be easily modified, including the number of turns, the distance between the coils d , and the outer diameter of the coil D , among others, allowing for rapid adjustments to the geometry and exploration of various solutions. Since the 2D simulations were made with the "planar" solver, some deviation is expected.

The software used is COMSOL Multiphysics. Firstly, the simulations were performed with current over the primary and a secondary with zero current, to simulate an open circuit. Secondly, a simulation is performed with current over the primary and a secondary with zero voltage, to simulate a short circuit in the secondary. Finally, with these two values of inductance, the leakage and magnetising inductances can be obtained with the set of equations shown in Equation 8, where a value is the measured turn ratio.

In this case, a simplification was made since it is a 1 to 1 turn ratio and the geometry of the IPT can be easily replicated in the prototype and manufacturing stage, $L_{1_L2open} = L_{2_L1open}$, with this simplification one simulation is saved.

$$a = \frac{L_{1_L2open}}{L_{2_L1open}} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & 1 & 0 \\ 1/a & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & a^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} L_m \\ L_{k1} \\ L_{k2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{1_L2open} \\ L_{2_L1open} \\ L_{1_L2short} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The criteria for selecting a double-D coil design include achieving the desired magnetising inductance while minimizing losses compared to the previous rectangular coil design. These losses include those associated with ferrite, wire, and shielding. To reduce

losses, a flux density limit of 0.15 T was set for the region between the coils and 0.1 T for other areas of the ferrite. These values are below the saturation point of the material.

However, wire losses increase in the double-D configuration as a result of the greater number of turns needed, necessitating a reduction in the number of turns per coil. Reducing the number of turns increases the magnetic flux density, so the chosen number of turns must ensure that the flux densities remain at or near the thresholds of 0.15 T and 0.1 T, as established.

The final design incorporates four turns per coil, totalling eight turns each for the primary and secondary windings. The outer diameter of each coil is set to 252.5 mm, with a distance d of 287.5 mm, resulting in a ratio of $d/D \approx 1.14$.

This configuration introduces an optimal spacing between the coils, maximizing the coupling coefficient to improve the overall efficiency of the system. Increasing the d/D ratio beyond 1.2 was determined to be impractical, as it would require a greater separation distance and additional ferrite material, resulting in minor returns in the coupling coefficient and, therefore, in efficiency. Hence, the selected dimensions represent a balanced trade-off between spatial requirements and performance enhancement.

The ferrite plane consists of a square plane with 550 mm of side. The loss distribution in the enclosure is shown in Figure 8, in which it can be seen that the maximum value is one order of magnitude less than the rectangular coil design, giving a total losses in the enclosure of 4.38 W. Also, the simulation reveals that only the stray flux is the one that is generating the losses and not the main flux that links the primary and secondary, as expected.

Figure 8. Volumetric losses in the IPT enclosure for double-D coil construction. Total losses equals to 4.38 W. The distribution of volumetric losses is an order of magnitude lower compared to the rectangular coil type.

In Figure 9 the distribution of the B field over the ferrites is shown. The maximum value of the B field is 0.12 T and it is located between the coils, as expected. This value is below the limits imposed to reduce the losses in the ferrite and also to ensure good magnetic behaviour.

Figure 9. Magnetic flux density (B) in the primary coils of the double-D coil configuration. The flux density is higher in the central region of the ferrite compared to its surroundings. This increase occurs because the coils in the same plane have currents flowing in the same direction, causing their generated flux to combine and increase the overall flux density.

5. Results comparison: Rectangular versus double-D design

To evaluate the improvement in efficiency and performance by adding this additional step in the design, a comparative analysis was performed that focused on key parameters at an operating temperature of 20 °C. Table 1 provides a detailed comparison of these key performance metrics, including total cable length, primary wire resistance, DC primary winding loss, magnetic flux density, ferrite losses, enclosure losses, and total losses for each design.

Table 1. Comparison between rectangular coil design and double-D design. Losses at 20 °C.

	rectangular coil	double-D
Total cable length (m)	7.52	9.22
Primary wire resistance (Ω)	4.93	6.04
DC windings loss (W)	98.6	120.8
DC+AC windings loss (W)	130.4	144.46
Mean B field (T)	0.065	0.085
Total core losses (3C95) (W)	34.17	101.04
Enclosure losses	269.6	4.38
Total Losses	434.17	249.88

The data in Table 1 reveal several key differences between the designs. The double-D coil requires a longer cable (9.22 m), which leads to higher DC resistance of the primary wire (6.04 Ω vs 4.93 Ω). Then, the losses in DC increase by the same percentage (22.5% increase) 60.4 W compared to 49.3 W in the rectangular coil. Taking into account the AC losses, obtained through FEM simulation, the difference between the rectangular coil and the double-D coil is 14.06 W.

This is due to the highest H field generated in the double-D coil where the two coils are close to each other. However, the double-D coil exhibits significantly lower enclosure losses (4.38 W vs. 269.6 W). Regarding total losses, double-D achieves a reduction in losses of 42.4 %, 249.88 W in the double-D coil versus 434.17 W in the rectangular coil.

This indicates that the double-D coil could be more suitable for applications focused on minimizing losses produced by the magnetic field impacting the enclosure walls, due to the capability of the double-D to focus the magnetic flux over a more defined magnetic path. This also helps to reduce the size of the enclosure, as the walls can be placed closer to the ferrites and coils. Meanwhile, the rectangular coil is better when the shield is not needed or has a great distance from the magnetic core, taking into account the gap between primary and secondary.

6. Conclusions

This study presented the design process for a high insulation, high frequency IPT system using a double-D coil design. The IPT increases the insulation while maintaining a good thermal behaviour compared to the traditional, MFT shell-type and core-type construction. The design consisted of several steps that involve first the acquisition of the inductance parameters using 2D simulations with a circular coil geometry. This inductance parameter allows for the obtainment of ZVS operation over the MOSFETs and consequently better efficiency. After this characterization, 3D simulations are performed to confirm the 2D script findings. To extend the design from circular/rectangular to double-D, additional steps have been added, performing another set of 2D simulations to study the relationship between coil diameter and coil distance (d/D), coupling and magnetising inductance.

For the last step, 3D simulations were performed to obtain the design with double-D that consists of four turns per coil, totalling eight turns each for the primary and secondary windings. The outer diameter of each coil is set to 252.5 mm, with a distance d of 287.5 mm in a ferrite plane of 550 mm, separated primary and secondary by 50 mm. The extra steps to obtain this double-D design prove to be advantageous, as the losses in the enclosure reduce 96% approximately and an overall loss reduction of 42.4%. Furthermore, the relationship between the center coil distance and the outer diameter of the coils d/D has revealed that the double-D can achieve better coupling if d/D is bigger than one, when the usual double-D construction uses a d/D equal to one.

Although this analysis provides valuable insights, further research is recommended to explore ferrite shielding configurations and improved cooling strategies that could further optimize IPT system performance. Furthermore, long-term durability testing conditions would be beneficial in assessing these findings and guide future design improvements in the MFT MV and IPT technology.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

MFT	Medium Frequency Transformer	
IPT	Induction Power Transfer	
SST	Solid State Transformer	
FEM	Finite Element Method	
ZVS	Zero Voltage Switching	
MV	Medium Voltage	
MOSFET	Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor	497
EV	Electric Vehicle	
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride	
HDPE	High-density Polyethylene	
DC	Direct Current	
AC	Alternating Current	

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